

Contextualising the Burkean Sublime in the Yapom of Galo Narratives

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Abstract:

The sublime is an aesthetic concept that describes experiences that are overwhelming, awe-inspiring, and often beyond human comprehension, a form of greatness that transcends ordinary limits and cannot be fully replicated or measured. The earliest known discussion of the Sublime appears in *On the Sublime*, attributed to Longinus (1st–3rd century CE), who saw it as the power of elevated language and thought to inspire awe and emotional intensity. Rediscovered in the 16th century and translated into French and English, this work laid the foundation for later philosophical exploration. In the 18th century, British thinkers like John Dennis, Shaftesbury, and Joseph Addison shifted the Sublime toward experiences of nature highlighting vastness, terror, and grandeur. Edmund Burke further developed the idea in *A Philosophical Enquiry (1757)*, arguing that the Sublime arises from feelings of awe, terror, and delight in the face of overwhelming power or obscurity.

This study investigates the Burkean Sublime as manifested in the figure of the *Yapom*, exploring how their overwhelming presence and dominion over nature evoke awe, terror, and wonder, key elements in Edmund Burke's conceptualisation of the Sublime."

The *Yapom* is one of the most prominent and expansive spirit races within the Galo cosmological framework, comprising multiple clans further divided into numerous sub-groups. They occupy a significant place in the Galo spirit realm, reflecting both the complexity and hierarchical structure of the supernatural world as perceived in Galo belief systems.

Methodology

This research utilises a blended methodology combining ethnographic fieldwork with literary analysis. The ethnographic aspect includes immersive interaction with the Galo community, conducting detailed interviews with cultural custodians, and critically examining the collected data through the theoretical lens of the Sublime.

Keywords: Contextualising, Yapom, Sublime, Nature, Awe-inspiring, Overwhelming, Profound, Untameable.

Introduction

The term *sublime* originates from the Latin word *sublimis*, meaning elevation or loftiness, and denotes a heightened state of consciousness often evoked by encounters with art or nature. Its conceptual roots trace back to antiquity, where it was seen as a force that elevates the soul through grand ideas and intense emotion. Enlightenment thinkers later expanded its scope, linking the sublime to human psychology and the emotional responses of awe, terror, and wonder when faced with overwhelming power or vastness. It came to represent the mind's confrontation with forces beyond comprehension, revealing the limits of perception and the transcendental reach of reason. For Longinus, the Sublime in art was not merely about replicating reality; rather, it was about the power of art to elevate the human soul, moving beyond ordinary experience and forging a connection to the extraordinary through grand thoughts and intense emotions. Edmund Burke in *A Philosophical Inquiry into the Origin of Our Ideas of the Sublime and Beautiful (1757)*, expands the scope of Sublime and includes aesthetic experiences in nature and art, linking the Sublime with human psychology and emotions, particularly terror. Later, Emmanuel Kant in *Critique of the Power of Judgment (1790)* examines Sublime in a broader aesthetic theory and positions the Sublime within a broader philosophical framework, focusing on the mind's response to the infinite or

the overpowering, highlighting the limitations of human perception and the transcendental capacity of reason. Burkean Sublime refers to the experiences that evoke terror often through vastness and incomprehensibility. For Burke, the Sublime involves an emotional reaction to encounters that challenge the mundane understanding. Drawing on Burke's classification of the Sublime, this paper contextualises the Burkean Sublime through the figure of the *Yapom*, the most formidable spirit race in the Galo narrative tradition, whose overwhelming presence is marked by an untameable and invincible force.

The Galo tribe of Arunachal Pradesh is one of the prominent communities in the region, known for its rich and complex body of folklore. Rooted in animistic beliefs, where every element of nature is considered animate and essential to the balance of existence, the Galo narrative tradition encapsulates the unique worldview of the tribe. This tradition encompasses a range of entities, including heroic and anti-heroic figures, powerful female forces, and awe-inspiring natural elements. Central to Galo cosmology are three parallel worlds: *Tani*, *Moko*, *Uiimoko*, and *Tale*. Each of these realms possesses its own distinct characteristics and spiritual significance. The *Yapom*, a formidable spirit race, inhabit *Tani Moko*, where they co-exist with many other spiritual beings and humans. The boundaries between the *Yapom(s)* and humans are fluid, marked by periodic interactions and complex relational dynamics.

According to Galo narratives, the *Yapom(s)* are believed to be descendants of *Taki*, the elder brother of *Tani*, the progenitor of the human race. This shared lineage positions the *Yapom(s)* and humans as cousins, establishing a kinship that accentuates many of their interactions. However, alternative accounts suggest that the *Yapom(s)* did not directly descend from *Taki* but rather originated from *Nyido*, the primordial rain. While the precise origin of the *Yapom* race remains a subject of ongoing oral debate and interpretive variation within the community, their prominent and enduring presence in the Galo cosmological framework is indisputable. Narratives portray the *Yapom(s)* as a diverse and complex race, encompassing clans that range from strikingly beautiful to grotesque and fearsome in appearance. Common descriptions depict them as long-haired beings with elongated noses and excessively long breasts, which they flip backwards over their shoulders like scarves due to their weight. Broad in stature and extraordinarily swift, *Yapom(s)* are believed to glide effortlessly through the air, a physical trait that reinforces their otherworldly nature. Despite their supernatural characteristics, it is said that the *Yapom(s)* live structured and socially organised lives much like humans. They are said to marry, raise children, and engage in various daily activities within their realm. Their sustenance comes primarily from fruits and certain other types of crops that are considered inedible to humans, and they are known to cultivate gardens, demonstrating a distinct affection for flowers, especially orchids. Trespassing to their orchards and gardens are seen as offence. However, Trespassers remain unharmed unless they take objects from the vicinity of their domain. They are also said to build their homes high in trees, and cutting down these trees without seeking permission is seen as a serious violation, often resulting in punishment. During farming, to avoid offending the *Yapom* and maintain harmonious coexistence, humans are required to perform the *Pombek* ritual. This ceremony serves as a symbolic acknowledgement of the *Yapom's* ownership over the land or resources humans wish to use, ensuring mutual respect and preventing any harm from befalling either side. Through this agreement, the *Yapom* and humans can coexist peacefully, with clear boundaries upheld.

The *Yapom(s)* are regarded as an immensely powerful race, possessing formidable control over the forces of nature. Galo narratives frequently attest to their invincible command over natural elements, illustrating their ability to summon storms, particularly in response to human trespassing or disrespect. Offenders are often afflicted with serious illnesses, believed to be spiritual punishments that can only be cured through the *Yapoms'* forgiveness, obtained via proper ritual mediation. In some accounts, the *Yapom(s)* are said to abduct individuals, trapping them indefinitely within their hidden villages. However, under certain conditions, especially when timely and respectful negotiations are carried out, they may choose to release their captives unharmed. These acts, oscillating between retribution and mercy, underscore the *Yapom's* sovereignty over the unseen world, as well as their complex moral agency within the Galo cosmological system.

The traditions say that *Yapom(s)* maintain deep reverence to the boundaries that were created as per the age-old accord made between *Tani* and the *Yapom(s)*; that is the reason why they are intolerant towards those who disrespect those boundaries. One significant narrative recounts a competition between *Tani* and the *Yapom(s)* over the rightful ownership of various types of land. This event takes place during *Tani's* progressive journey into agriculture, following his acquisition of grains and cultivation knowledge from Goddess *Mopin* in her divine land. As *Tani* sought to plant these grains in *Tani Moko*, the *Yapom(s)* resisted, leading to a confrontation. With divine support from *Mopin* and the use of strategies, *Tani* ultimately emerged as the winner. This victory resulted in the formal delineation of territory: humans (*Tani's* descendants) were granted dominion over the plains and cultivable lands, while the *Yapom(s)* were assigned the deep forests, difficult mountains, uninhabited by humans.

Since then, it is believed that the *Yapom(s)* have abided by these boundaries with silent reverence, maintaining their existence in anonymity, detached from human affairs unless provoked. Yet, human encounters with the *Yapom(s)* persist, often unwillingly or unknowingly trespassing into their domains, resulting in various forms of sublime interactions.

These interactions take various forms, ranging from instances where humans trespass into *Yapom* territory and suffer severe retributions, to situations where *Yapom(s)* act as guardians during human stays in the forest. In some accounts, individuals lose their way in the wilderness and never return, believed to be held under the spell of the *Yapoms*. In contrast, other narratives portray them as compassionate beings, offering healing and assistance out of affection or empathy.

Such diverse human-*Yapom* interactions exemplify the sublime in nature as conceptualised by Edmund Burke, wherein the obscurity, power, and unpredictability of the *Yapom(s)* evoke a profound emotional response that oscillates between awe and fear. The *Yapoms'* incomprehensible nature, their resistance to human control, and their deep connection to untamed landscapes place them firmly within the realm of the Burkean sublime beings whose presence is both terrifying and wondrous, and whose engagement with humans reveals the limits of human perception and power in the face of the supernatural.

In *A Philosophical Inquiry into the Origin of Our Ideas of the Sublime and Beautiful* (1757), Burke describes various means through which the sublime is experienced, namely: (i) sublime in obscurity and vastness, (ii) sublime, through beauty and terror and (iii) sublime through terror and danger. However, the paper explores the sublime in the presence of the *Yapom(s)*, in its one particular form, i.e. Sublime through beauty and terror,

The paper explores the sublime's manifestations within the Galo natural world through *Yapom's* invocation of beauty and terror. Burke says that the Sublime often emerges from the tension between beauty and terror, where the overwhelming and unsettling qualities of terror overshadow the elegance and grace of beauty. He writes, "WHATEVER is fitted in any sort to excite the ideas of pain and danger; that is to say, whatever is in any sort terrible or is conversant about terrible objects, or operates in a manner analogous to terror, is a source of the Sublime" (Burke [1757]1823,45). In the many narratives associated with the *Yapom(s)*, the arrivals or displeasure of the *Yapom(s)* over human intrusions are sensed through storms and sudden darkening of the skies. Such displays, though causing no direct physical harm, command awe and induce an instinctive fear, revealing the *Yapom's* mastery over elemental forces. Their dominion does not require violence; rather, it lies in their ability to bend nature to their will, unsettling human perception of the natural world. This overwhelming display of untameable power, both magnificent and terrifying, reflects the very core of the Sublime. The *Yapom* do not just inhabit the wilderness; they animate it, asserting an invisible but omnipotent presence that makes the familiar uncanny, the beautiful fearsome, and the natural supernaturally charged.

The Sublime quality of the *Yapom* is further revealed through their dual nature, capable of benevolence and terror. In certain narratives, they appear as compassionate figures who restore health and peace to those they favour, even forming emotional bonds with humans. These acts, performed without expectation of reciprocity, reflect an ethereal beauty and selflessness that enchants and overwhelms. However, this enchantment often carries an undercurrent of danger. When the true identity or appearance of a seemingly kind *Yapom* is unveiled, the shift from beauty to grotesque horror intensifies when provoked, the Sublime experience, where attraction quickly turns into fear.

The *Yapom*'s intimate relationship with the environment also reflects their dual embodiment of the Sublime. Their guardianship over delicate and unworldly flora, such as orchids cultivated in sacred groves, represents their nurturing side. The overwhelming beauty of these flowers often captivates human intruders, leading to transgressive acts that disrupt the harmony between the human and supernatural realms. Such trespasses are not without consequence. The *Yapom*'s retribution manifested through illness, madness, or near-death experiences reveals the terror inherent in violating natural or spiritual boundaries.

Conclusion

The *Yapom*, in their power to both enchant and destroy, represent the full spectrum of the Sublime, demanding respect, humility, and reverence from those who encounter them.

Thus, the *Yapom* stand as sublime agents of the Galo imagination, beings whose presence fuses wonder with dread, and whose dominion over nature renders them both revered and feared, reminding us that in the heart of beauty often lies the shadow of terror.

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